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Identification of AR-interacting proteins.

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We employed a proteomic approach to understanding the full range of molecules that interact with the Androgen Receptor (AR). We report here identification of an AR-interacting protein network that functions in variant form in hormone receptor-positive cancer in males with prostate cancer and in females with breast cancer. We describe a broad range of factors participating in the AR-interaction network including KDM1A, FOXA1, NCOA2, NCOA3, NCOA4, NCOR1, NCOR2, EP300 and SRC.